

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF NATIVE (LIQUID) AND CONCENTRATED UP TO 40 % VINASSE AS A RAW MATERIAL FOR ANAEROBIC FERMENTATION

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Abstracts

The energy crisis that is currently taking place in Ukraine requires an active search for alternative energy sources. Ukraine provides itself with natural gas and oil of its own production only by 20 %. With the help of biogas technologies, it is possible to increase the share of energy from renewable sources, reduce the amount of waste generation, and limit greenhouse gas emissions. Biogas is produced as a result of methane fermentation of biomass. There is a significant problem with the waste of bioethanol production – beet vinasse, a dark-colored liquid with an unpleasant odor. Anaerobic fermentation technologies are the basis for the disposal of organic waste in the world. Vinasse concentration is one of the alternatives with which can be the efficiency of anaerobic digestion and reduce the negative economic and environmental consequences of applying large volumes of vinasse in the fields. Studies show that concentrated vinasse is more suitable for methane fermentation than liquid vinasse. The process of concentrating vinasse is economically beneficial for plants, as it will reduce the size and cost of building biogas reactors and can facilitate the management and processing of vinasse. An additional advantage of using methanogenesis for waste utilization is obtaining the digestate – the product after methane fermentation and obtaining the main product – biogas. It can also be successfully used in agriculture as a fertilizer. It has many nutrients and does not pollute the environment, as it is free from fermentation products. The proposed technologies will allow sugar and alcohol plants to carry out waste-free production, receiving the main product biogas to meet their own energy needs, and digestate.

Keywords: biogas, anaerobic digestion, methane fermentation, methanogenesis, beet vinasse, molasses bard, waste of bioethanol production, concentrated vinasse, digestate, fertilizer.

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1. Introduction

The current energy crisis in Ukraine requires an active search for alternative energy sources. Bioenergy has a number of advantages: energy independence and stability: energy production does not depend on weather conditions; can be used as a balancing power. Development of local economy: new jobs and additional budget revenues. Income for farmers: purchase of local biomass from agricultural producers. Fulfillment of international obligations: fight against climate change and reduction of CO₂ emissions.

Ukraine is only 20 % self-sufficient in natural gas and oil of its own production. The price of alternative energy is 3 to 17 times lower than energy from traditional sources [1].

Anaerobic fermentation technologies are the basis for the disposal of organic waste in the world. These technologies are universal with a high level of development. Since Ukraine has considerable potential for the implementation of such technologies, but does not have sufficient experience, their implementation, implementation of pilot projects in the main regions of the country can be the first step towards their rapid dissemination.

Biogas technologies can increase the share of energy from renewable sources, reduce waste generation and limit greenhouse gas emissions. According to the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine [2], there are only 50 biogas projects in Ukraine in 2021. This is almost 50 % more biogas plants compared to 2020 (27 biogas projects). The total installed electric capacity of biogas plants in Ukraine is more than 86 MW, it has increased by 23.25 % compared to 2020. The

electric capacity of individual projects reaches up to 12 MW. The implemented projects of biogas complexes in the agricultural sector are mainly focused on the production of electricity and its sale at a “green” tariff.

Biogas, according to the Law of Ukraine “On Alternative Fuels” [3], is a gas derived from biomass used as fuel. Biogas obtained from organic raw materials in the process of biomethanogenesis is a mixture of 65...75 % methane and 20...35 % carbon dioxide, as well as a small amount of hydrogen sulfide, nitrogen, hydrogen. Purified biogas is similar to natural gas. Environmental safety of use and caloric content of biogas combined with the simplicity of the technology of its production, as well as a huge amount of waste to be recycled – all this is a positive factor for the further development and expansion of the biogas industry.

Biogas potential and composition are highly dependent on the raw material. Biogas is produced as a result of methane fermentation of biomass (biological material available on a renewable basis), which can generally be divided into waste, residues and individual energy crops.

There is a significant problem with the waste of bioethanol production - beet vinasse, a dark liquid with acidic pH and high content of volatile substances with an unpleasant odor. Vinasse is the main liquid by-product of the sugar-ethanol industry [4]. It is a highly coloured effluent consisting of water (93 %) and rich in nutrients (mainly potassium) and organic matter (7 %), which can be highly polluting when released into the environment [5, 6]. A large amount of vinasse is produced, from 10 to 15 liters per liter of ethanol produced [7].

In Ukraine, such bard (vinasse) is discharged to filtration fields, which use fertile land, in addition, these fields become a source of pollution of surface water bodies and air, especially in the warm season. This method of disposal, in addition to harming the environment, brings direct losses to producers, and also significantly reduces tourist interest in Ukraine due to the deterioration of living standards. According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, in 2020, more than 500 thousand tons of vinasse was poured onto filtration fields, which led to CO₂ emissions and a decrease in the quality of life of people. Molasses bard at only one of the plants (SE “Haisyn Distillery”) is formed in the amount of 800 m³ per day and poured onto the filtration fields, so it needs to be disposed of.

One of the alternatives that was adopted at some plants is to reduce the volume of vinasse by evaporation [7]. Due to its high COD (chemical oxygen demand) content, anaerobic digestion of vinasse has become an alternative to treat this by-product, producing methane that can be used to increase the energy produced in sugar-ethanol plants. Anaerobic digestion has demonstrated the potential of organic waste utilization as a renewable energy source [8, 9]. The concentration of vinasse, and thus the increase of COD content in the substrate, can increase the anaerobic efficiency of fermentation and reduce the amount of vinasse applied per hectare, reduce the size and costs of the reactors and facilitate the management and handling of this by-product.

The concentration of vinasse is another alternative with which to integrate anaerobic digestion and further increase the efficiency of this process and reduce the negative economic and environmental impacts of applying large amounts of vinasse to sugarcane fields [10].

Our research presents beet vinasse, because in European countries ethanol production from sugar beet is more represented than from sugar cane. Therefore, more beet vinasse is produced and more interested in its processing and utilization [11].

Concentration of beet vinasse was performed on a rotary evaporator. On the basis of the State Enterprise “Haisyn distillery”, Vinnytsia region.

Digestate, the product after methane fermentation and obtaining the main product – biogas, can also be successfully used in agriculture as a fertilizer. It has many nutrients and does not pollute the environment, as it is free from fermentation products.

2. Materials and methods

The humidity of molasses bard (vinasse) was determined by drying the sample at a temperature of 105 °C in a drying oven to a constant weight [12]. Ash content of vinasse was determined by burning the sample in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 550 °C until complete ashing, fol-

lowed by determining the amount of unburnt residue [13]. The content of total Nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl method [14, 15]. The crude protein content was determined by determining the total nitrogen content by the Kjeldahl method (DSTU ISO 1871:2003) and multiplying the result by a factor of 5.7 [16, 17].

The direct substrate for biogas synthesis is organic dry matter (ODM). Their content can be calculated by the formula [18]:

$$\text{ODM(\%)} = 100 \% - \text{substrate moisture (\%)} - \text{ash content (\%)}. \quad (1)$$

The result is the percentage of organic components such as protein, fat and carbohydrates.

Total carbon (C) was determined by the Pregla method. According to this method, vapors of substances are oxidized by passing them in a mixture with oxygen through a layer of copper oxide and lead chromate heated to 750 °C and placed in a combustion tube.

The sulfate content was determined by the complexometric method [19, 20]. Of all the complexometric methods for the determination of sulfate ions, the most reliable results, especially in the analysis of polluted wastewater, are given by the method proposed by Belcher, modified and supplemented by Y. Lurie and Z. Nikolayeva. The essence of the method: in this method, sulfate ions are precipitated with barium chloride solution, the barium sulfate precipitate is filtered, washed, dissolved in alkaline EDTA solution and the excess of the latter is titrated with magnesium chloride solution.

Vinasa (molasses bard) was provided by the State Enterprise “Haysyn distillery”, produced in February-March, stored in a freezer at a temperature of $-16 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Before the study it was defrosted at room temperature for 2–3 hours. This company, as well as a number of others in Ukraine are interested in obtaining results on the use of vinasse. Concentration of beet vinasse was performed on a rotary evaporator at the State Enterprise “Haisyn distillery”, Vinnytsia region.

The physicochemical parameters of digestates obtained in the process of methane fermentation were investigated in the framework of comparing native and concentrated vinasse, as well as two digestates obtained at existing biogas plants in Ukraine, to find out the theoretical nutritional value of these products after anaerobic fermentation for soil:

1) Liquid filtered digestate fraction from the Integro-SD biogas plant in Kozhukhivka village, Kyiv region. Integro-SD was founded in 2002 on the basis of the MacHOUSE agricultural holding (Ukraine) and specializes in the production of organic fertilizer from chicken manure “Humino de gallina” (Italian gallina – chicken). In 2019, Integro-SD received a grant under the Climate Innovation Vouchers project, implemented by the NGO Greencubator with the support of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the European Union, which allowed to automate production. The company produces biofertilizer by anaerobic thermophilic fermentation of the substrate, thus obtaining biogas (45 m³/day) as a by-product to provide heat for production.

2) The liquid fraction of the digestate from the Biogas complex for the processing of organic waste with a capacity of 6 MW/h of the I&U Group agricultural holding (Kapitanivka village, Novomyrhorod district, Kirovohrad region). The biogas complex began operation in 2020 and supplies energy to the Ukrainian power grid at a “green” tariff. At the beginning of operation, half of the plant operated in thermophilic mode, the mirror half – in mesophilic mode, but in the same year it was decided to completely switch to mesophilic mode due to more stable fermentation.

The main purpose of the biogas complex is the processing of waste from the sugar plant of the same agricultural holding “Novomyrhorod Sugar”, namely sugar beet pulp. Also, during the design and construction of the biogas complex, its expansion was provided for further use of waste from the Kapitanivska poultry farm. Currently, silage corn serves as a co-substrate for beet pulp, but in the future it is also planned to replace it with organic waste or residues of energy crops to obtain additional bonuses for the export of biomethane.

Digestates were stored in hermetically sealed canisters at a temperature of 4 °C and immediately before introduction into the experiment were gradually heated for 2 hours at room temperature in closed flasks. To determine the pH of the liquid digestates, a portable pH/ORP meter pH58 (Milwaukee, Hungary) was used, calibrated with two standard buffer solutions with pH 7.01 and pH 4.01.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of the substrate

A number of analyses were carried out on native (liquid) beet vinasse and vinasse concentrated to 40 % dry matter to compare them as potential substrates for methane (anaerobic) fermentation to produce renewable fuel – biogas. The concentrated vinasse was pre-diluted 5 times with distilled water, directly for analyses. The results are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table 1

Physicochemical parameters of native and 4 times concentrated vinasse

Parameters	Native vinasse	Concentrated vinasse
Dry matter, %	10.85±0.02	40.10±0.05
Moisture, % d.s.	89.15±2.51	59.90±2.63
Ashes, % d.s.	3.03±0.05	16.84±0.05
Carbon, % d.s.	45.95±2.11	64.26±2.48
Nitrogen, % d.s.	8.51±0.40	10.71±0.31
C/N (ratio)	5.4	6.0
Sulfur, % d.s.	3.48±0.12	2.86±0.10
VFA, % d.s.	7.82±0.33	23.26±0.40

The dry matter content of vinasse increased from 10.85±0.02 % to 40.10±0.05 % after vacuum evaporation. Let's calculate the dry matter content (DM) by subtracting the moisture content of the substrate for anaerobic digestion (in our study – native and concentrated vinasse) from 100 %.

Very important for methane fermentation is the indicator of organic dry matter (ODM). Let's calculate the organic dry matter (ODM) content by the formula

$$\text{ODM}(\%) = 100\% - \text{substrate moisture}(\%) - \text{ash content}(\%) \quad (2)$$

The content of dry matter, and hence organic dry matter (ODM), in the vinasse increased, which is certainly a positive factor, since an important indicator for methane fermentation is the ODM, because these substances will be directly subjected to fermentation and conversion into target products.

In addition, the process of vinasse concentration is economically advantageous for the plants, as it will reduce the size and construction costs of biogas reactors and can facilitate the management and handling of a by-product such as vinasse (beet molasses bard).

The vinasse evaporation process slightly increased the C/N ratio, from 5.4 to 6.0, which can cause a positive effect on the fermentation performance. The optimal range of C/N ratio is indicated as 25 to 35 for biogas production. However, in the case of sugar beet vinasse there is a high nitrogen content, which makes the C/N ratio below the optimal range. The process of vinasse evaporation, although insignificant, brings the substrate to a more optimal carbon to nitrogen ratio, which will ensure that anaerobic fermentation will be more complete and increase the yield of the final product – biogas.

The inorganic sulfur content (in ash) after vinasse concentration decreases in dry matter from 2.50 % to 1.87 % due to sedimentation in the form of potassium sulfate. The organic sulphur content was approximately 1 % DM in vinasse before evaporation and this did not change significantly.

The high sulphur content in the vinasse is due to the addition of 5–10 kg of sulphuric acid per ton of sugar beet molasses during the ethanol production stage, which is necessary to optimize the pH and to avoid the development of non-target microorganisms. Also due to thermodynamic reasons, at low acetate concentrations, sulfate-reducing bacteria produce hydrogen and acetate more easily than methane-forming bacteria, which leads to increased sulfide levels that inhibit methane fermentation [8].

The problem of high sulfur content, as it is possible to see from the analysis results, can be solved by concentrating vinasse 4 times.

The evaporation process slightly increases the C/N ratio and decreases the sulfur content. Although the vinasse concentration increased, the more optimal C/N ratio facilitated the separation of the inhibitory source of sulfur compounds.

A very important indicator of the substrate for anaerobic fermentation is the indicator of volatile fatty acids (VFA). Volatile fatty acids are one of the main substances from which biogas is formed.

In order to explain the importance of volatile fatty acids for methane fermentation, it is necessary to explain a little bit the nature of the processes that occur during the anaerobic fermentation of any substrate. Very simplified, anaerobic fermentation for biogas production consists of the following steps:

1. Hydrolysis of natural polymers and complex substances with the formation of volatile fatty acids.

2. Conversion of VFA into biogas at the next stage of methanogenesis.

That is, VFA is a building material for methanogenesis.

At these stages, the biological agents are two groups of microorganisms – hydrolytic and methane (biogas) forming. They are conditionally connected by the food chain: the products of the first (VFA) are nutrition for the second.

As can be seen from the table, concentrated vinasse contains three times more volatile fatty acids (VFA) in comparison with native, i.e. raw, vinasse up to 23.26 % of dry matter against 7.82 %, which is much better for further methane fermentation.

However, not everything is so clear about the importance of volatile fatty acids (VFA) for methane fermentation.

There are three more circumstances that critically affect the course of fermentation:

1. The rate of hydrolysis is several times higher than the rate of methanogenesis, and, accordingly, the growth rate of active biomass.

2. Methanogens are easily washed out of the reactor due to the fact that gas bubbles on the surface of the cells carry them to the surface of the liquid and out of the reactor.

3. Excessive concentrations of VFA that are formed suppress methanogens until the process stops completely - “preservation” of the reactor contents may occur. That is, the substrate will be peroxidized, but the process of methanogenesis will not go.

Thus, for native, raw, vinasse, these circumstances greatly affect the process of biogas production. In the first two points, an important role is played by the fact that the substrate (native vinasse) is very moist (89.15 %), which contributes to rapid hydrolysis, a large amount of volatile fatty acids is formed at once and methanogens at the next stage of conversion do not have time to digest such a large amount of fatty acids into biogas and eventually partially washed out of the reactor.

It is in the case of a sharp increase in the amount of volatile fatty acids that the process mentioned in point 3, the “preservation” of the reactor contents, may occur. That is, on the one hand, volatile fatty acids are good, because they are the building blocks for biogas production, and on the other hand, the process should be slower so that all methanogens have time to react and digest the fatty acids into biogas. And in the case of native vinasse, the fact that the process will not go according to plan is quite likely.

However, these statements slightly change their meaning in the case of concentrated vinasse. It is 4 times more concentrated than liquid vinasse, so hydrolysis proceeds more slowly in

it, volatile fatty acids are produced in larger quantities, but not immediately, but gradually, methanogens have time to digest them. Methanogens are not washed out of the reactor due to the less liquid environment, they are retained in the reactor and the process is more complete. In this case, the process of “conservation” does not occur, because at all stages everything happens slower, but with a greater final result.

3. 2. Methane fermentation

In the framework of our study, experiments on anaerobic fermentation of native and 4 times concentrated vinasse were carried out on the basis of the State Enterprise “Haisyn distillery”. According to the results of fermentation to depict the process, the corresponding graphs were built.

The summary indicators of the process during the periodic methane fermentation of native, i.e. liquid, vinasse, as well as the yield of methane and carbon dioxide during the process, are shown in the graphs below (Fig. 1–3).

Fig. 1. Anaerobic fermentation of native vinasse. Yield of biogas, ml

Fig. 2. Anaerobic fermentation of native vinasse. Yield of biogas, %

As can be seen from the graphs, the maximum biogas yield when using native vinasse is provided on the 15th day. Later the process slowed down and then stopped altogether.

A very important indicator of the completeness and correct direction of the methane fermentation process is the it is possible to see from Fig. 3, the yield of methane in the final product, biogas, is in the range of 78–80 %, and carbon dioxide, respectively, 10–15 %, which confirms the indicators of these components indicated in the literature.

The summary indicators of the process during the periodic methane fermentation of 4 times concentrated vinasse, as well as the yield of methane and carbon dioxide during the process, are shown in the graphs below (Fig. 4–6).

As can be seen from **Fig. 4, 5**, anaerobic fermentation of concentrated vinasse was active until day 20. This can be explained by the fact that in a denser substrate, concentrated 4 times vinasse, compared to liquid vinasse, the process was slower, but more complete.

Regarding the important indicator of methane fermentation, as the ratio of methane and carbon dioxide in biogas, it can be seen from **Fig. 3–6** that the methane yield, during the fermentation of concentrated vinasse, reached the maximum values already from day 10 and did not decrease, maintaining a stable 80 % of methane in the biogas produced.

Fig. 3. Anaerobic fermentation of native vinasse. Ratio CO₂, CH₄, %

Fig. 4. Anaerobic fermentation of 4 times concentrated vinasse. Yield of biogas, ml

Fig. 5. Anaerobic fermentation of 4 times concentrated vinasse. Yield of biogas, %

Fig. 6. Anaerobic fermentation of 4 times concentrated vinasse. Ratio CO₂, CH₄, %

3. 3. Digestate

After methane fermentation and obtaining the main potentially energy product, biogas, the digestate remains, which is free from fermentation products, that is, it will not clog the environment with decay processes. It can be successfully used as an organic fertilizer, as it contains many nutrients that will contribute to soil enrichment and crop improvement.

According to the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine [2], digestate after anaerobic digestion contains:

- organic carbon, including humic substances (1...3 % by weight) a complex of macro- and micronutrients necessary for plants (N, P, K, Mg, S);
- increases the yield of agricultural crops in comparison with mineral fertilizers;
- high share of nitrogen available for plants (up to +10...70 % compared to non-fermented materials);
- optimal for soil C:N ratio=20...30;
- optimal pH value for the soil is 6.8...7.5;
- contains active populations of bacteria that contribute to the decomposition of organic matter in the soil;
- moisture (promotes the penetration of nutrients into the soil, including fertilizers);
- helps to reduce the density and increase the moisture retention capacity of soils;
- potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (up to 6 kg CO₂ eq per 1 kg of substituted nitrogen fertilizers).

The digestate obtained after anaerobic digestion during the study was analyzed. The results are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2

Physicochemical parameters of digestate

Indicator	Univ. dimension	Digestate after methane fermentation
Dry substances	g/kg	46,4
Organic substances	g/kg	24,8
pH	–	7,97
C/N	–	3,5
Total fatty acids	g/l	4,89

Based on the obtained indicators, it is possible to conclude that the obtained digestate contains many nutrients, that is, it will enrich the soil, has a more or less neutral pH, which will not change the pH of the soil. In addition, the level of volatile fatty acids is low, which will not contribute to fermentation and pollution of the environment.

The digestate obtained at two operating biogas plants in Ukraine was also analyzed: Liquid filtered fraction of digestate from the Integro-SD biogas plant in Kozhukhivka village, Kyiv region and Liquid fraction of digestate from the 6 MW/h biogas complex for processing organic waste of the I&U Group agricultural holding (Kapitanivka village, Novomyrhorod district, Kirovograd region).

The results are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3

Physicochemical parameters of digestate from biogas plants

Digestate type	Dry matter, %	Ash content, % of dry matter	pH
Integro-SD	3.01±0.00	0.043±0.003	8.74±0.03
Agricultural Holding I&U Group	3.78±0.04	0.028±0.008	8.40±0.05

The dry matter content was 20 % lower in the liquid fraction of the Integro-SD digestate. There are two main reasons for this. First, the fine substrate compared to the energy plants of the biogas plant in Kapitanivka. Secondly (and perhaps this is the main thing): Integro-SD digestate is used as a biofertilizer, so the liquid fraction of Integro-SD digestate is additionally filtered so that when used for drip irrigation of plants, the digestate does not clog the openings of the equipment.

As a result of the analyses of the digestate, it can be concluded that it will positively affect the soil condition and increase the yield. However, biogas producers cannot sell digestate widely yet, as there is no official certification of digestate in Ukraine. But for their own or others' fields, their own needs, they can successfully use the digestate as an organic fertilizer. In Ukraine, there is a positive experience of using digestate as an organic fertilizer. The increase in yields reached 30–40 %.

Limitations of the study: the research was conducted on the basis of the Laboratory of Biotechnology of Biofuels and Innovations in Green Energy, Department of Genomics and Molecular Biotechnology State Institution "Institute of Food Biotechnology and Genomics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine". Laboratory installations for anaerobic fermentation were built for the research. What could not be done in laboratory conditions, in fact, this is, in my opinion, the limitation of the study, was carried out on the basis of an operating alcohol plant in Ukraine.

Prospects for further research: in the future it is planned to improve the technology of anaerobic digestion of vinasse depending on the needs and wishes of specific enterprises of ethanol and sugar industry. Based on the results of the study, an evaporator plant for vinasse concentration and a biogas plant for further use of the concentrated vinasse for anaerobic digestion are already being designed. There are plans to add lignocellulosic raw materials to vinasse as a feedstock for anaerobic fermentation to increase the carbon to nitrogen ratio and, accordingly, increase the biogas yield.

4. Conclusions

The use of biogas technologies in the context of the energy crisis in Ukraine allows to increase the share of energy from renewable sources, and is characterized by simplicity and speed of repair. The process does not depend on weather conditions and external factors.

The production of biogas from molasses – the main liquid by-product of the sugar-ethanol industry – will significantly improve the environment, as it eliminates the ingress of unprocessed molasses on fertile land. Thus, it is possible to solve both economic and environmental problems of the enterprise and humanity in general. Biogas production from waste will reduce the amount of waste generation and limit greenhouse gas emissions. Thus, the environmental concept of "Zero effluent" – zero discharges is being implemented.

After obtaining the main product – biogas – digestate remains, which not only does not pollute the environment, as it is free from fermentation products, but can also be used as a fertilizer,

which will positively affect the yield, and will help agriculture to save on organic fertilizers. In Ukraine, there is a positive experience of using digestate as an organic fertilizer. The increase in yields reached 30–40 %.

The process of vinasse evaporation brings the substrate to a more optimal ratio of carbon and nitrogen, which will ensure a more complete anaerobic fermentation and increase the yield of the final product – biogas. As it is possible to see from the results of the study, in the case of concentrated vinasse, 2 times more biogas was obtained compared to native vinasse (7500 and 3600 ml, respectively).

The process of anaerobic fermentation in the case of concentrated vinasse is more uniform, methanogenesis (formation of the main product in biogas – methane) is more stable.

The vinasse concentration process is economically advantageous for the plants, as it will reduce the size and construction cost of biogas reactors and can facilitate the management and handling of by-products such as vinasse (beet molasses bard).

Based on the results of the study, an evaporator plant for vinasse concentration and a biogas plant for further use of the concentrated vinasse for anaerobic digestion are already being designed.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

References

- [1] Feduniak, I. O. (2014). Efficiency of biogas production in Ukraine. Scientific Notes of the National University of Ostroh Academy. Series “Economics”: collection of scientific papers, 26, 45–49.
- [2] Bioenergy Association of Ukraine UABIO (2021). Bioenergy facilities: infographic. Available at: <https://uabio.org/materials/11862/>
- [3] Law of Ukraine “On Alternative Fuels” No. 1391- VI of 21.05.2009. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1391-14#Text>
- [4] Moraes, B. S., Zaiat, M., Bonomi, A. (2015). Anaerobic digestion of vinasse from sugarcane ethanol production in Brazil: Challenges and perspectives. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 44, 888–903. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.01.023>
- [5] Laime, E., Fernandes, P., Oliveira, D., Freire, E. (2011). Technological possibilities for the destination of vinasse: a review. *Rev Trópica Ciências Agrárias e Biológicas*, 5, 16–29.
- [6] Romanholo Ferreira, L. F., Aguiar, M. M., Messias, T. G., Pompeu, G. B., Queijeiro Lopez, A. M., Silva, D. P., Monteiro, R. T. (2011). Evaluation of sugar-cane vinasse treated with *Pleurotus sajor-caju* utilizing aquatic organisms as toxicological indicators. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 74 (1), 132–137. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2010.08.042>
- [7] da Silva, A., Rossetto, R., Bonnacine, J., Piemonte, M., Muraoka, T. (2012). Net and Potential Nitrogen Mineralization in Soil with Sugarcane Vinasse. *Sugar Tech*, 15 (2), 159–164. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12355-012-0199-0>
- [8] Ta, A. T., Babel, S. (2019). Utilization of green waste from vegetable market for biomethane production: influences of feedstock to inoculum ratios and alkalinity. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 21 (6), 1391–1401. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-019-00898-2>
- [9] Sica, P., Carvalho, R., Das, K. C., Baptista, A. S. (2020). Biogas and biofertilizer from vinasse: making sugarcane ethanol even more sustainable. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 22 (5), 1427–1433. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-020-01029-y>

- [10] Renewable Energy Statistics 2019 (2019). Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates: The International Renewable Energy Agency, 382.
- [11] Maurya, R., Tirkey, S. R., Rajapitamahuni, S., Ghosh, A., Mishra, S. (2019). Recent Advances and Future Prospective of Biogas Production. *Advances in Feedstock Conversion Technologies for Alternative Fuels and Bioproducts*, 159–178. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-817937-6.00009-6>
- [12] Petersburgsky, A. V. (1968). *Workshop on Agronomic Chemistry*. Moscow: Kolos.
- [13] Smirnov, V. O., Sergeyev, P. V., Biletsky, V. S. (2011). *Technology of coal enrichment*. Donetsk: Eastern Publishing House, 476.
- [14] DSTU ISO 1871:2003. *Agricultural food products. General guidelines for the determination of nitrogen content by the Kjeldahl method (ISO 1871:1975, IDT)*.
- [15] Mazor, L. (1986). *Methods of organic analysis*. Moscow: Mir, 333–337.
- [16] Volynets, V. F., Volynets, M. P. (1977). *Analytical chemistry of nitrogen*. Moscow: Nauka, 54–55.
- [17] Nechaev, A., Traubenberg, S., Kochetkova, A. (2007). *Food chemistry*. Saint Petersburg: GIORD.
- [18] Kulichkova, G. I., Ivanova, T. S., Köttner, M., Volodko, O. I., Spivak, S. I., Tsygankov, S. P., Blume, Y. B. (2020). Plant Feedstocks and their Biogas Production Potentials. *The Open Agriculture Journal*, 14 (1), 219–234. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874331502014010219>
- [19] Lurie, Y. Y. (1984). *Analytical chemistry of industrial wastewater*. Moscow: Chemistry.
- [20] Yulevich, O. I., Kovtun, S. I., Gil, M. I. (2012). *Biotechnology*. Mykolaiv: MDAU, 476.

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